

DISEASES OF THE UPPER RESPIRATORY TRACT IN LIVESTOCK AS A RESULT OF WORK ON LIVESTOCK FARMS.

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Abstract. *The article describes the specifics of the activities of livestock farms, the factors that negatively affect them. Negative factors: noise, humidity, high and low temperature, wind speed, forced labor conditions were checked and analyzed. The research was conducted among a total of 26 employees of 2 livestock farms and 4 employees of the district center for the control group. The survey used anonymous surveys of workers and data from the district's Sanitary and Epidemiological Surveillance and Public Health Department. According to the results of the research, the results of anonymous surveys of livestock and the data of the District Sanitary and Epidemiological Surveillance and Public Health According to the department's conclusion, negative factors in the work process can actually cause livestock diseases.*

Key words: *livestock, negative factors, humidity, temperature, noise.*

ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ВЕРХНИХ ДЫХАТЕЛЬНЫХ ПУТЕЙ У СКОТА КАК РЕЗУЛЬТАТ РАБОТЫ НА ЖИВОТНОВОДЧЕСКИХ ФЕРМАХ.

Аннотация. *В статье описывается специфика деятельности животноводческих ферм, факторы, которые отрицательно на них влияют. Были проверены и проанализированы негативные факторы: шум, влажность, высокая и низкая температура, скорость ветра, условия принудительного труда. Исследование проводилось среди 26 работников 2 животноводческих ферм и 4 работников районного центра для контрольной группы. При опросе использовались анонимные опросы работников и данные районного управления санэпиднадзора и общественного здоровья. По результатам исследования были использованы результаты анонимных опросов скота и данные районного управления санэпиднадзора и общественного здоровья. По заключению отдела, негативные факторы в процессе работы действительно могут вызывать заболевания скота.*

Ключевые слова: *скот, негативные факторы, влажность, температура, шум.*

Relevance. The territory of Uzbekistan belongs to the 4th geographical zone -the sharp continental - hot climate zone. The climate in our region varies according to the seasons. [1]

Cattle breeders spend most of their working time outdoors, that farm workers are exposed to very hot summers and very cold winters, that their work schedules are not clearly planned, and that they are in constant contact with animals, is a part of their work. is a characteristic feature.

These properties have a negative effect on their body. [2]

Animal husbandry is one of the most important branches of world agriculture. Livestock industry is spread all over the world like cereal crops. Meadows and pastures in agricultural lands occupy three times more land than arable lands. Therefore, the bulk of livestock production is grown in temperate countries. [3]

In particular, today livestock breeding is of special importance in Uzbekistan.

All types of animal husbandry are developed. In particular: astrakhan, leather, dairy cattle, meat cattle, meat and dairy cattle, horse breeding, camel breeding and other areas. Livestock plays an important role in the country's agriculture. [4]

Purpose of the work. The purpose of scientific research is to identify the specifics of the activities of livestock breeders, to study the negative factors affecting livestock breeders, to improve measures to prevent negative factors affecting workers on livestock farms.

Research methods. The research was conducted among ranchers. 11 employees of the 1st livestock farm and 15 employees of the 2nd livestock farm in the district and 4 managers of the district center of both farms were hired for the control group.

Workers' activities were observed in spring, summer, autumn, and winter. Harmful factors in their work: wind speed, high and low temperatures, humidity, solar radiation, noise, forced working conditions were studied. External environmental factors were checked using special instruments (psychrometer, anemometer, thermometer, barometer, shumomer - ISHV 1, aspirators). An anonymous survey was conducted to determine the changes in the body of livestock as a result of adverse factors affecting their work. During the research, work was carried out in collaboration with the district sanitary-epidemiological and public health staff, and their annual data were used. [6]

Research results. The results of the inspection revealed the following: in the 1st livestock farm the maximum temperature in summer is + 48 °C, the minimum temperature in winter is -11 °C; Livestock farm No. 2 has a maximum temperature of + 49 °C in summer and a minimum temperature of -12 °C in winter, and workers are outdoors at this temperature. Temperature in summer and winter seasons in the district Annual temperature changes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Seasonal temperature changes in the work process of livestock breeders (at °C)

	Temperature in the first half of spring	Temperature in the second half of spring	Temperature in summer	Temperature in the first half of autumn	Temperature in the second half of autumn	Temperature in winter
1-economy	+ 25 ± 3	+ 35 ± 3	+ 44 ± 4	+ 36 ± 2	+ 14 ± 2	- 8 ± 3
2 -economy	+ 26 ± 3	+ 36 ± 3	+ 45 ± 4	+ 37 ± 2	+ 15 ± 2	-9 ± 3
The control group in the district center	+ 23 ± 3	+ 25 ± 3	+ 30 ± 2	+ 25 ± 2	+ 21 ± 2	+ 20 ± 2

In summer, humidity in farms is 30-35%; In winter, humidity reaches 70-75%. The humidity in the workplaces of the employees in the center is 40-60%.

The wind speed at the workplaces of farms 1 and 2 is 10 – 14 m / sec. The wind speed at the workplace is 0.1 - 0.3 m / s.

The noise of the equipment of the milkers, tanners and shearers of the 1st farm is 95-100 dB, the noise of the equipment of the 2nd farm in the same industries is 98 – 105 dB. Workers in the control group had a workplace noise level of 15 - 25 dB. In some areas of farms, the dust level is 27 mg/m³, the dust does not contain SiO₂. [7]

It was found that workers work 10 hours a day without shifts, milkers and shearers are mainly forced to work. Livestock breeders do not use personal protective equipment during labor.

According to the results of an anonymous survey of sanitary-epidemiological control and health authorities: 2 workers from farm 1 had a heat stroke in summer, 3 had inflammation of the upper respiratory tract in winter, 1 milkmaid and 1 noise disease in one wool shearer, varicose veins of the legs due to forced labor in 2 workers; Three workers from Farm 2 were found to have heat stroke in summer, 2 from upper respiratory tract inflammation in winter, 1 from skin rashes, and 2 from wool cutters. It was found that the above cases were not observed in 4 employees of the control group. [8]

Discussions. Investigations have shown that herders do not have regular working hours, are not provided with personal protective equipment, are forced to work for most of the work process, work in the open air at high temperatures in summer and low temperatures in winter.

High-frequency noise, abnormal humidity and wind speed, high levels of allergens have had a detrimental effect on livestock. Employees working in the district center are not affected by negative factors during their work. Their working hours are standardized. They do not work outdoors during high and low temperatures. As a result, employers were not adversely affected by negative business processes.

Conclusions. Based on the above information, we conclude that the specific features that affect the work process in livestock farms are the lack of standardized working hours, lack of personal protective equipment, forced labor and negative factors that negatively affect the labor process. And these factors, in fact, can cause disease in livestock.

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